

It means, therefore, that with an increase of DMSO in the system the concentration of positive cobalt complex increases, thus resulting in the low adsorption of the metal ion on resin.

Based on these distribution studies few separations were tried, as a result some important separations have been achieved which are, summarized in Table I.

TABLE I—QUANTITATIVE SEPARATION OF SYNTHETIC MIXTURES ON DOWEX MACROPOROUS RESIN, MSA-1 COLUMNS (i.d., 4.0×0.8 cm) WITH ELUENT FLOW RATE OF 0.2 ml PER MINUTE

Metal Ions Separated	Taken μg	Found* μg	Eluent	Volume ml
Tl(I)-	202.4	202.3±0.20	E3	50
In(III)	50.8	50.8±0.05	E4	20
Tl(I)-	40.5	40.5±0.05	E3	26
In(III)	203.2	202.2±0.15	E1	40
Tl(I)-	202.4	202.3±0.20	E3	50
Zn(II)	65.0	65.1±0.05	E1	24
Tl(I)-	40.5	40.5±0.05	E3	26
Zn(II)	260.0	260±0.15	E1	40
Tl(I)-	240.5	240.5±0.15	E3	50
Cd(II)	112.5	112.5±0.12	E4	20
Tl(I)	40.5	40.5±0.05	E3	26
Cd(II)	250.0	250.0±0.30	E4	36
Tl(I)-	240.5	240.5±0.25	E3	50
Hg(II)	40.0	40.0±0.10	E1	24
Tl(I)-	40.5	40.5±0.10	E3	26
Hg(II)	400.0	400.0±0.15	E1	45
Mn(II)-	110.0	110.0±0.20	E3	36
Co(II)	110.0	110.0±0.25	E1	60
Mn(II)-	110.0	110.0±0.20	E3	35
Fe(III)	140.0	140.0±0.15	E1	45

* Mean of triplicate determinations with calculated standard deviation.
 E1—1.0M NH₄SCN—80%DMSO, 0.5M HCl—60%DMSO
 E3—0.05M NH₄SCN ; 0.05 EDTA.

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Decomposition of Alcohols over Ceria

A. SUBRAMANIAN, K. NARAYANAN and M. R. UDUPA

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Madras-600 036

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EXTENSIVE studies have been made on the decomposition of alcohols over alumina and thoria catalysts¹⁻³ and it is observed that they act as dehydration catalysts both for cyclic and acyclic alcohols. The literature survey on this aspect is scanty⁴ and the previous results are all patented. We report in this note, the decomposition of menthol and the substituted pentanols over ceria catalysts obtained by different preparative routes.

Experimental

Three types of catalysts namely, ceria-I, ceria-II and ceria-III were obtained by air-heating for 8 hours at 800°, freshly prepared Ce(OH)₃ and Ce(C₂O₄) and AnalaR Ce(NO₃)₄.2NH₄NO₃.2H₂O respectively. The X-ray powder patterns of the catalyst samples were taken using a Debye-Scherrer Camera of 11.46 cm diam. and CuK_α radiation. The specific surface area measurements of the catalysts were obtained by volumetric method⁵ using nitrogen gas as the sorbate at liquid nitrogen temperature and using BET equation. A flow-type catalytic reactor was employed for the decomposition reactions of alcohols, with the weights of the catalysts, the temperature and the flow-rate being constant. The analyses of the products of alcohol decomposition over ceria catalysts were carried out using Varian 700 VA and 1800 VA gas chromatographs.

Results and Discussion

The X-ray diffraction patterns of the three ceria samples are quite identical and the d_{hkl} values (Å), 3.12s, 2.71m, 1.92s, 1.64s ; 1.57w, 1.36w, 1.25w and

1.11w agreed with the reported⁶ values of CeO_2 . The specific surface area values (m^2g^{-1}) 7.2 (ceria-I), 7.4 (ceria-II) and 7.3 (ceria-III), are also the same within the experimental error and are very low. The products of decomposition of alcohols over ceria are found to be olefines and ketones as obtained in the dehydration and dehydrogenation respectively. Thus, cyclohexanol gives a mixture of cyclohexene and cyclohexanone and menthol decomposes to menthenes and menthone. 3-Methyl-2-pentanol on dehydration gives a mixture of isomers namely 3-methyl-1-pentene and 3-methyl-2-pentene (*cis* and *trans*) whereas 4-methyl-2-pentanol dehydrates to give 4-methyl-1-pentene and 4-methyl-2-pentene (*cis* and *trans*). These two alcohols on dehydrogenation afforded methylpentanones. The tertiary alcohol 3-methyl-3-pentanol, was found to undergo only dehydration to give 3-methyl-2-pentene. The results of the analyses of the corresponding olefines and ketones, the products of alcohol decomposition over thoria, are given in Table 1. The results suggest that the three ceria

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Dielectric Polarisation of Alkylquinolines and Molecular Interaction in Solution

A. N. SRIVASTAVA, A. K. MEHTA
and

SUNIL KUMAR GARG

Department of Chemistry, University of Jodhpur,
Jodhpur

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TABLE 1—DECOMPOSITION OF ALCOHOLS OVER CERIA

Alcohol	Catalyst	Conversion %	Product Dehydration olefines*	Distribution (%) Dehydrogenation ketones**
Menthol	Ceria-I	39	33	67
	Ceria-II	40	29	71
	Ceria-III	35	29	71
3-Methyl-2-pentanol	Ceria-I	90	25	75
	Ceria-II	75	30	70
	Ceria-III	70	35	65
4-Methyl-2-pentanol	Ceria-I	15	36	64
	Ceria-II	17	40	60
	Ceria-III	14	36	64
3-Methyl-3-pentanol	Ceria-I	88	100	—
	Ceria-II	86	100	—
	Ceria-III	86	100	—

Catalyst weight: 5 gms; Flow-rate: 12 ml hr⁻¹; Temp.: 360-375°

* Olefines obtainable from the different alcohols have been enumerated in the text.

**The ketone obtainable from the different alcohols have also been listed out in the text.

samples behave more or less similarly towards a particular alcohol. The per cent conversion under the conditions of the experiment is minimum for 4-methyl-2-pentanol and is maximum for 3-methyl-3-pentanol. Excepting in the case of the tertiary alcohol, 3-methyl-3-pentanol, other three alcohols undergo both dehydration and dehydrogenation, the latter being twice as that of the former process.

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A survey of literature¹ reveals that in past dielectric measurements have been carried out only on 2-methyl quinoline in benzene. Consequently our attention was drawn to carry out such measurements on other alkyl quinolines in non-polar solvents. The primary object of the present investigation was to study the interaction between solute and solvent involving the π -electron system of the solutes reported earlier².

Experimental

The method and technique have been described elsewhere^{3,4}.

Results and Discussion

The variation of moments in solution have been discussed in the light of Higasi's theory^{5,6,7} using the data of tensor ellipsoid for quinoline along three principal axes as $b_1=1.64$, $b_2=2.29$ and $b_3=0.75$.

Fig. 1. Direction of Tensor Ellipsoids.

The theory suggests that the ratio of semiaxes c and a for quinoline very with tensor ellipsoid values